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Recent applications of the hetero Diels-Alder reaction in the total synthesis of natural products

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Abstract

The synthetic utility and potential power of the Diels-Alder (D-A) reaction in organic chemistry is evident. These significances have been extended to the synthesis of a plethora and wide variety of heterocyclic compounds via [4 + 2] cycloaddition reactions, the so called hetero Diels-Alder (HDA) reaction. In this work we try to focus on the scope and preparative synthetic applications of the HDA reaction as a key step in the total synthesis of natural products.

Keywords

Cycloaddition, Hetero Diels-Alder reaction, Hetero-diels-Alder, Heterocyclic compound, Natural products, Organic Chemistry, Synthetic application, Synthetic utility, [4 + 2] cycloaddition, Synthesis (chemical)